

ANALYSIS OF TECHNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF MULTI-FACETED WAFFLE WEAVING

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Abstract: *The article provides a complete plan of the waffle cut fabric based on the actual cuts, as well as the calculation of the weight of the resulting tissue.*

Keywords: *waffle cutting, backing, weaving, coating, board image*

In order to expand the range of waffle weaving and to improve the quality of weaving and effective use of the technological capabilities of the weaving machine "VAMATEX" on the basis of waffle weaving on the basis of waffle weaving 3 units were created and produced, raw as $T_t = 18.5 \times 2$ tex; A cotton yarn with a linear density of $T_a = 27$ tex was used. The density of the fabric on the back is $R_a = 200$ yarn / 10 cm, the number of blades used is $N_b = 80$. All samples are made on a loom "VAMATEX" with a working width of 190 cm, produced by the Italian company ITEMA.

In the course of our study, the structure of the waffle weave was characterized by the appearance of a multi-faceted shape of the fabric due to the inclusion of rows of coatings in the center of the body and the direction of the back. we have mentioned that improvement has been achieved.

In the study, it was proposed to add rows of coatings in the center to the body and back direction to the waffle braid tissue structure to enhance the capillary properties of the waffle braid tissue, resulting in multi-faceted shape views. In order to expand the range of waffle weaving, capillary and multi-faceted appearance of the fabric on the loom "VAMATEX" in the center of the waffle weave and back rows of coatings 3 different variants of the fabric were produced by comparing the technological parameters and physical and mechanical properties of the produced waffle weaving samples. Multi-

faceted waffle weaving patterns were produced by inserting rows of coatings in the center (Fig. 2-3).

Tt = 18.5x2 tex linen density cotton yarn was used as the body yarn, and Ta = 27 tex linear density cotton yarn was used as the back yarn. the calculation of Sample 1 is given. To produce the sample of variant 1, we add 1 row of coatings in the center to the direction of the body on the basis of the current shear S1 / 4, shear S =

Hence: $R\bar{b}=1+4=5$, $S=1$

$$R_T = (2 \cdot R_B - 2) + H_{\text{Табл}} \quad (1)$$

$$R_T = (2 \cdot R_B - 2) + 1 = 9$$

$$R_a = 2 \cdot R_b - 2 = 8$$

A complete board image of the produced multi-sided waffle cutting fabric is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

The calculation of Sample 2, which is obtained by inserting rows of coatings in the center in the direction of the back of the waffle-cut fabric produced, is also given. To produce the variant 2, we add 1 row of coatings

in the center to the back direction on the basis of the current shear $S1 / 4$, the shear $S = 1$.

Hence: $R\bar{6}=1+4=5$, $S=1$

$$R_T = 2 \cdot R_{\bar{6}} - 2 = 8$$

$$R_a = (2 \cdot R_{\bar{6}} - 2) + H_{apK}$$

$$R_a = (2 \cdot R_{\bar{6}} - 2) + 1 = 9$$

A complete board image of the produced multi-sided waffle cutting fabric is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2

the calculation of the waffle-cut texture of the 3 samples produced was obtained by inserting rows of coatings in the center in the direction of the body and back.

For the production of option 3, we add 1 row of coatings in the center to the body and back direction on the basis of the current weave Sarja $S1 / 4$, shear $S = 1$.

Hence: $R\bar{6}=5$, $S=1$

$$R_T = 2 \cdot R_{\bar{6}} - 2 = 8$$

(2)

$$R_{t,a} = (2 \cdot R_b - 2) + H_{t,a}$$
$$R_{t,a} = (2 \cdot 5 - 2) + 1 = 9 \quad (3)$$

A complete board image of the produced multi-sided waffle cutting fabric is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Technological parameters and physical and mechanical properties of the samples were determined by the standard method in the testing laboratory "Textile" at the Namangan Engineering and Technology Institute, and the results are given in Table 1.

The surface density of the tissue is traditionally calculated according to the raw material consumption criterion. It is known that an increase in the surface density of waffle cut tissue leads to a change in its physical and mechanical properties. Therefore, weight indicators describing the raw material consumption and quality indicators of the tissue are included at the same time.

The weights of the waffle cut fabric are pagon meters, square meters, and volumetric weights.

The weight characteristics of the multi-faceted waffle braided fabric with different structure are different for each sample.

Calculate the weight of the tissue in the current tissue

The weight of a pagon meter tissue

$$M^1 = \frac{B_{\text{ном}} \cdot M}{L} = \frac{184.99 \cdot 141}{100} = 261 \text{ г/пог. м}$$

Weight of one square meter of tissue

$$M_1 = \frac{10^6 \cdot M}{L \cdot B} = \frac{10^6 \cdot 1.41}{100 \cdot 100} = 141 \text{ г/м}^2$$

Dimensional weight of tissue.

$$\delta = \frac{10^3 \cdot M}{L \cdot B \cdot b} = \frac{10^3 \cdot 1.41}{100 \cdot 100 \cdot 2.176} = 0.064 \text{ мг/мм}^3$$

1 Sample texture

The weight of a pagon meter tissue

$$M^1 = \frac{B_{\text{ном}} \cdot M}{L} = \frac{184.99 \cdot 174}{100} = 322 \text{ г/пог. м}$$

Weight of one square meter of tissue

$$M_1 = \frac{10^6 \cdot M}{L \cdot B} = \frac{10^6 \cdot 1.74}{100 \cdot 100} = 174 \text{ г/м}^2$$

Dimensional weight of tissue.

$$\delta = \frac{10^3 \cdot M}{L \cdot B \cdot b} = \frac{10^3 \cdot 1.74}{100 \cdot 100 \cdot 2.176} = 0.079 \text{ мг/мм}^3$$

2 Sample texture

The weight of a pagon meter tissue

$$M^1 = \frac{B_{\text{ном}} \cdot M}{L} = \frac{184.99 \cdot 177}{100} = 327 \text{ г/пог. м}$$

Weight of one square meter of tissue

$$M_1 = \frac{10^6 \cdot M}{L \cdot B} = \frac{10^6 \cdot 1.77}{100 \cdot 100} = 177 \text{ г/м}^2$$

Dimensional weight of tissue.

$$\delta = \frac{10^3 \cdot M}{L \cdot B \cdot b} = \frac{10^3 \cdot 1.77}{100 \cdot 100 \cdot 2.104} = 0.084 \text{ мг/мм}^3$$

3-sample texture

The weight of a pogan meter tissue

$$M^1 = \frac{B_{\text{xom}} \cdot M}{L} = \frac{184.99 \cdot 185}{100} = 342 \text{ г/пог. м}$$

Weight of one square meter of tissue

$$M_1 = \frac{10^6 \cdot M}{L \cdot B} = \frac{10^6 \cdot 1.85}{100 \cdot 100} = 185 \text{ г/м}^2$$

Dimensional weight of tissue.

$$\delta = \frac{10^3 \cdot M}{L \cdot B \cdot b} = \frac{10^3 \cdot 1.85}{100 \cdot 100 \cdot 3.281} = 0.056 \text{ мг/мм}^3$$

Table 1

	Samples	Sample weight (gr.)	The weight of a pogan meter tissue (g / m)	Weight of one square meter of tissue (g / m ²)	Dimensional density of tissue. (mg / mm ³)
1	Current	1.41	261	141	0.064
2	1-sample	1.74	322	174	0.079
3	2-sample	1.77	327	177	0.084
4	3-sample	1.85	342	185	0.083

Technological parameters and physical and mechanical properties of the produced samples

As can be seen from this table, the weight of the recommended multi-faceted waffle cuts is higher than that of the existing fabric. Especially in Example 3, its weight was increased due to the increase in the number of coatings in the body and back direction, as well as the thickness of the added yarns.

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